

Laser Wakefield Acceleration Simulation as a Service

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Abstract

The research area of laser wakefield acceleration of electrons is characterized by non-linear processes, which makes it difficult to find optimal parameters for stable and best possible beam quality. Also to support experimental results with simulations and to perform sensitivity analysis large systematic studies are desired. For this studies, in-situ analyses are necessary that allow performing a large part of the analysis during the simulation time.

In this master thesis, both an in-situ analysis, the emittance plugin, for determining transversal projected emittance as well as slice emittance of the electron beam and a tool for simple execution of systematic studies, the PIConGPU GUI, are developed. For the visualization of the emittance values, different classes that are used by the PIConGPU GUI were written by the author. The PIConGPU GUI allows to set simulation parameters easily via a graphical user interface (GUI), start, manage and analyse many different simulations on a cluster. This allows to automatise large systematic studies that can be performed easily and by any user. In order to demonstrate the benefit and functionality of the new tool, the first large parameter scans were performed and analysed. In the regime of the density down-ramp injection the influence of the focus position of the laser, the laser strength parameter a_0 and the length of the density down-ramp Δx on the energy, energy spread and charge of the injected electron bunch as well as the maximum energy reached and the projected emittance is determined.

Zusammenfassung

Das Forschungsgebiet der Laser-Wakefield-Beschleunigung von Elektronen ist durch nichtlineare Prozesse gekennzeichnet, welche die Suche nach optimalen Parametereinstellungen für eine stabile und bestmögliche Strahlqualität erschweren. Ebenso zum Vergleich experimenteller Ergebnisse mit Simulationen und Durchführung von Sensitivitätsanalysen, sind große systematische Studien notwendig. Diese erfordern neben einem schnellen Simulationscode in-situ-Analysen, mit welchen ein großer Teil der Analyse während der Simulationszeit durchführbar wird.

In dieser Masterarbeit werden sowohl eine in-situ-Analyse, das Emittanz-Plugin zur Bestimmung der projizierten Emittanz sowie der Slice-Emittanz des Elektronenstrahls als auch ein Werkzeug zur einfachen Durchführung systematischer Studien, die PIconGPU GUI, entwickelt. Für die Visualisierung der Emittanzen wurden vom Autor verschiedene Klassen geschrieben, die von der PIconGPU GUI verwendet werden. Die PIconGPU GUI erlaubt es, Simulationsparameter einfach über eine grafische Benutzeroberfläche (GUI) einzustellen, viele verschiedene Simulationen auf einem Cluster zu starten, zu verwalten und zu analysieren. Dies ermöglicht die Automatisierung großer systematischer Studien, die einfach und von jedem Benutzer durchgeführt werden können.

Um den Nutzen und die Funktionalität des neuen Tools zu demonstrieren, wurden die ersten großen Parameterscans durchgeführt und analysiert. Im Regime der Dichte-down-ramp-Injektion wird der Einfluss der Fokusposition des Lasers, des Laserstärkeparameters a_0 und der Länge der down-ramp Δx auf die Energie, Energieausbreitung und Ladung des injizierten Elektronenbunches sowie die maximal erreichte Energie und die projizierte Emittanz bestimmt.

1. Motivation

Laser Wakefield Acceleration (LWFA) promises up to four orders of magnitude smaller and thus significantly more cost-effective electron accelerators for research, industry and medical technology. It is important to know the effects of small fluctuations of input parameters on the results and to be able to reconstruct the experiments with simulations. The possibility to search for the optimal setup for such accelerators with large parameter scans brings the goal of generating particle beams useful for applications within reach. For large systematic studies, however, the usual approach to start every simulation manually, store all relevant data and evaluate it afterwards is no longer feasible. Because one simulation easily results in several TB of data, leading to a data volume of over 100 TB with a variation of only two parameters with ten sample points each. Just reading this data, would take about a week at a reading speed of 250 MB/s. Thus, systematic studies would easily exceed both time limits and storage capacities. This problem is solved by in-situ analyses and storing only the results of analyses which are already carried out during the simulation time. Since not all particle and field data have to be stored, the simulation time and the memory requirements reach a level where systematic studies are possible. In this master thesis, an in-situ analysis for the determination of emittance as well as the slice emittance is developed. Moreover a tool to easily execute and analyse systematic studies like parameter scans, sensitivity analyses or comparison to experimental results has been developed in the context of this thesis. In order to demonstrate the benefit and functionality of such a new tool, large parameter scans are performed and analysed. The time and memory savings of the in-situ analyses in connection with systematic studies enable a wide range of users to perform many automated simulations simultaneously.

2. Introduction

Particle accelerators are an essential tool in science. They are not only part of the large particle colliders, but also of many scientific and medical instruments such as synchrotrons or free-electron lasers. Accelerators enable advances in engineering, medicine and in the biological and physical sciences. Apart from particle physics, they are used for example in material science, cancer treatment or as synchrotron light sources [1, 2, 3]. Most prominent and powerful are the large-scale accelerators, like LHC at CERN and Tevatron at Fermilab, used as research tools in high energy physics. These accelerators use electromagnetic fields at radio frequencies in normally or super-conducting cavities to accelerate charged particles. However, conventional accelerators are presently limited to acceleration gradients of 100 MV/m by the material breakdown limit due to field emission of electrons from surface impurities [4]. Consequently, the energy gained per length is strongly limited and long acceleration distances are required to reach high particle energies. For example, the largest linear accelerator SLAC in California was able to accelerate electrons up to 50 GeV but measured a length of 3.2 km [5]. Currently, there are more than 30,000 accelerators in operation around the world [6], even if much space is needed and costs are enormous to build and operate such facilities. In order to handle both issues alternative smaller and more cost-effective acceleration schemes are required. One of these is the laser-plasma acceleration proposed by Tajima and Dawson in 1979 [7]. This concept promises significantly smaller acceleration length by benefiting from very large electric fields that are with 100 GV/m [8] about 3-4 magnitudes higher than in conventional accelerators. In laser-plasma acceleration, a short intense laser pulse creates a plasma wave with a phase velocity close to the speed of light. The acceleration of electrons in this strong plasma wave is called **laser wakefield acceleration** (LWFA). The

strong longitudinal electric fields used in this process are not limited by vacuum breakdown[9], because of the already ionized plasma. The energies obtained in compact LWFAs are sufficient for applications like free electron lasers [10] or x-ray radiation sources [11]. To fulfill the requirements of these applications a minimal transverse momentum spread is required while maximizing the energy of the electron bunch. Already laser intensities of 10^{18} W/cm², which can be reached by current technology, force the electrons to move at relativistic velocities. At these energies, the laser-plasma interaction becomes nonlinear [8]. This makes it challenging to analytically predict an optimal setup where the electron beam will have the best quality. Therefore performing simulations is the only feasible way to model all details of the complex plasma dynamics [12].

The **Particle-In-Cell** (PIC) method models the mutual interaction between electromagnetic fields and charged particles. The particle-in-cell code PIConGPU provides a framework to study, among others, relativistic LWFA by handling large-scale simulations and using thousands of GPUs [13]. This makes PIConGPU about an order of magnitude faster than other particle-in-cell codes running on commodity clusters.

In the usual approach to evaluate simulations, the field and particle data are analyzed after the simulation. Therefore it is necessary to store a large amount of data in order to extract all relevant information afterwards. In contrast to this there is the approach to calculate the interesting quantities already during the simulation and thus to reduce the amount of data to be stored. This is possible with so-called **in-situ analyses**. For example, for a LWFA simulation in which the necessary data is stored for evaluation in post-processing, approx. 700 GB of memory and 160 min of simulation time are required. In contrast, an in-situ analysis can reduce the memory requirement to 1.5 %. This also shortens the simulation time to 68%, since the time to write data is reduced.

With the increase in computational speed as well as the time and memory savings, extensive **systematic studies** become possible [14]. These large parameter surveys or **systematic studies** are desired for predicting optimized parameters, supporting experimental results and perform sensitivity analyses. In **parameter scans**, input parameters are varied over a larger range, with the aim of finding a point at which optimal results can be obtained. With the help of **sensitivity analyses** it is possible to investigate parameters strongly influence the beam parameters by varying input parameters. For this purpose, several simulations are performed in which the input parameters are only varied within a small range. Furthermore, systematic studies can be used to **support an experiment** and to

compare to the experimental results. For this purpose, the input parameters of the experiment are set in several simulations, in which they are varied by their possible uncertainties.

To empower every researcher to easily perform parameter surveys and analyse their simulations, an **new online tool** is needed that simplifies simulations, visualizations and analysis. This tool has to start the systematic study, distribute the simulations to the queues in the cluster and offer a selection of visualizations to enable an easy and fast evaluation.

This master thesis demonstrates that such parameters studies, which can be started and evaluated via an online tool, are now possible. First the physical basics are introduced in **chapter 3** to provide the basis for the evaluation of the performed parameter scan. In **chapter 4** the simulation algorithm is introduced as well as different possibilities to analyze and visualize the simulation results. In this chapter, the in-situ analysis for the determination of emittance as well as the slice emittance, which is developed in the context of this work, is further presented. The online tool with which it is possible to start systematic studies is also demonstrated. By running parameter scans the benefit and functionality of this new tool for easy control of systematic studies, is demonstrated in **chapter 5** using the example of down-ramp injection in LWFA. In the regime of the density down-ramp injection the influence of the focus position of the laser, the laser strength parameter a_0 and the length of the density down-ramp Δx on the energy, energy spread and charge of the injected electron bunch as well as the maximum energy reached and the projected emittance are determined with three large parameter scans.

3. Physical introduction to laser wakefield acceleration

The first concept of laser wakefield acceleration (LWFA) was proposed by Tajima and Dawson in 1979 [8]. The idea of LWFA is based on electric fields, that are sustained by electron density modulations, to accelerate charged particles. These plasma waves can be excited by intense laser pulses or by energetic particle beams. This thesis focuses on the physics scenario of LWFA. In this scheme short laser pulses (≈ 30 fs) with sufficiently high intensities ($> 10^{18} \frac{\text{W}}{\text{cm}^2}$) propagate through a gas (figure 3.1.1) and ionize the gas at the front of the pulse, which is possible for intensities starting at $\approx 10^{14} \frac{\text{W}}{\text{cm}^2}$. Thus the main pulse interacts with a fully ionized plasma.

3.1. Laser parameters

As an example of a laser profile used in a real experiment, a Gaussian radial profile could be assumed in the simulation. For this profile figure 3.1.2 shows the beam width as a function of the distance z along the beam. Here the normalized vector potential of the laser field $\vec{a} = e\vec{A}/m_e c^2$ is given by a Gaussian function, where \vec{A} is the magnetic vector potential and m_e is the electron mass. Near the focus the vector potential can be described by

$$\vec{a} = a_0 \exp\left(\frac{-r^2}{w(z)^2}\right) \exp\left(\frac{-(z-ct)^2}{c^2\tau^2}\right) \cos(kz - \omega t) \vec{e}_r, \quad (3.1.1)$$

with w_0 being the beam waist or spot size, that parameterizes the beam diameter in the focus [8]. The peak amplitude of the vector potential of the laser field \vec{a} is defined by the laser strength parameter a_0 . It is related to the peak laser intensity I_0 by [8]

$$I_0 = \frac{4\pi^2 c \epsilon_0}{2} \left(\frac{m_e c^2 a_0}{e \lambda} \right)^2. \quad (3.1.2)$$

Furthermore, with the peak laser electric field amplitude E_0 , a_0 can be derived from [8]

$$a_0 = \frac{E_0 e}{m_e c \omega_L}. \quad (3.1.3)$$

Starting with the force of an electron interacting with the laser field $E_L(t) = E_0 \sin(\omega_0 t)$, the maximal electron momentum within a plane wave with amplitude E_0 can be derived.

$$\frac{dp}{dt} = e \cdot E_L(t) \quad (3.1.4)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow p_{max} = \frac{eE_0}{\omega} \quad (3.1.5)$$

Figure 3.1.1.: Scheme of laser wakefield acceleration (LWFA). The laser pulse propagates through a gas jet, ionizes the gas and generates plasma waves. In this wave electrons are accelerated, which leave the gas at the end. Graphic designed by A. Debus, K. Steiniger, R. Pausch

Figure 3.1.2.: Gaussian beam width $w(z)$ as a function of the distance z along the beam. w_0 : beam waist; Z_R : Rayleigh length. Graphic based on [17].

An electron can reach a relativistic momentum for

$$m_e c \leq p_{max} = e E_0 / \omega \quad (3.1.6)$$

$$\Rightarrow 1 \leq \frac{e E_0}{\omega m_e c} \quad (3.1.7)$$

$$\Rightarrow 1 \leq a_0. \quad (3.1.8)$$

This leads to the convention to distinguish between intensities of $a_0 < 1$, called the non-relativistic regime, and $a_0 > 1$, where the quiver motion of a plasma electrons is relativistic and the laser-plasma interaction becomes nonlinear. For example for a wavelength of $\lambda = 0.8 \mu\text{m}$ relativistic electron motion requires laser intensities of $I \geq 2 \cdot 10^{18} \text{W/cm}^2$.

When a laser propagates through a plasma, it will displace electrons by the ponderomotive force (see next section) and thus transfer laser energy to the plasma. The energy loss over time leads to a limited penetration depth of the laser in the plasma. This is called depletion length and is one of the limitations of LWFA experiments. As follows the depletion length depends both on the intensity of the laser and on the density of the plasma, and thus on a_0 and λ_p [15, 16].

$$L_{depletion} \approx \frac{\lambda_p^3}{\lambda_0^2} \begin{cases} \sqrt{2} a_0 / \pi & : a_0 \gg 1 \\ 2 / a_0^2 & : a_0 \ll 1 \end{cases} \quad (3.1.9)$$

3.2. Ponderomotive force

When the main laser pulse interacts with a fully ionized plasma, it excites large amplitude plasma waves via the ponderomotive force. The ponderomotive force is an averaged force on an electron and can be derived in the non-relativistic case by considering the equation of motion of an electron with the mass m_e , charge e and velocity \vec{v} in an electromagnetic field:

$$m_e \frac{d\vec{v}}{dt} = -e [\vec{E}(\vec{x}, t) + \vec{v} \times \vec{B}(\vec{x}, t)]. \quad (3.2.1)$$

The right side of the equation corresponds to the Lorentz force F_L , which takes in cgs units the form

$$\vec{F}_L = -e [\vec{E}(\vec{x}, t) + \frac{\vec{v}}{c} \times \vec{B}(\vec{x}, t)] \quad (3.2.2)$$

where c is the speed of light in vacuum. This shows that the $\vec{v} \times \vec{B}$ term only becomes relevant at electron velocities close to the speed of light, because in cgs units \vec{E} and \vec{B} have the same order of magnitude. In order to achieve relativistic velocities, lasers with high intensities are necessary. The realization of the required laser intensities becomes possible through the development of terawatt laser systems with Chirped-Pulse Amplification (CPA) technology, that was first applied by Strickland and Mourou in 1985 [18]. This achievement brought plasma-based accelerators to the attention of research groups worldwide in the 1990s. Nowadays there are ongoing experimental programs for example in France [19], Germany [20], Japan [21] and the United States [22].

To derive the ponderomotive force, the first and second order of Taylor expansion of equation (3.2.1) is formed by assuming a wave electric field of the form $\vec{E} = \vec{E}_0(\vec{x}) \cos \omega t$ [23].

$$\text{first term Taylor expansion : } m \frac{d\vec{v}}{dt} = -e \vec{E}_0(\vec{x}_0) \sin \omega_L t \quad (3.2.3)$$

$$\text{second term Taylor expansion : } m \frac{d\vec{v}}{dt} = -e [(\delta \vec{x}_1 \cdot \vec{\nabla}) \vec{E}_0(\vec{x}_0, t) + \vec{v}_1 \times \vec{B}_1], \quad (3.2.4)$$

where ω_L is the laser frequency and \vec{v}_1, \vec{B}_1 are the first order values. Since the ponderomotive force corresponds to the time-averaged force, the terms of the Taylor expansion and the ponderomotive force f_{pond} follow as

$$m \left\langle \frac{d\vec{v}}{dt} \right\rangle = 0 \quad (3.2.5)$$

$$m \left\langle \frac{d\vec{v}}{dt} \right\rangle = \frac{-e^2}{4m\omega_L^2} \underbrace{\nabla |\vec{E}_0(\vec{x})|^2}_{\propto \nabla I} = f_{pond}. \quad (3.2.6)$$

Figure 3.3.1.: Scheme for the formation of plasma waves in LWFA. The ponderomotive force of the laser deflects the electrons transversally, forming a bubble behind the laser. In this figure almost all electrons were removed from the bubble and a positive cavity is formed from the ion background. Inside the bubble an electron bunch is accelerated. This image was created with PIconGPU.

This shows that the ponderomotive force is proportional to the negative gradient of intensity. Thus the electrons are accelerated to lower intensities. Here f_{pond} is the effective nonlinear force on a single electron. The force F_{pond} per m^3 results from multiplying f_{pond} by the electron density. For a gaussian laser profile one applies $E_0^2 = 2\langle E^2 \rangle$ and with the plasma frequency $\omega_p = \sqrt{\frac{n_p e^2}{\epsilon_0 m_e}}$ remains [23]:

$$F_{pond} = \frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega_L^2} \nabla \frac{\langle \epsilon_0 E^2 \rangle}{2} \quad (3.2.7)$$

The ponderomotive force can also be viewed as a radiation pressure, that pushes away the free plasma electrons.

3.3. Plasma waves

While the electrons are pushed back by the ponderomotive force, the much heavier ions of the plasma remain stationary. Thus, the electrons are subsequently pulled back towards their original positions by the positive ions, but their

Figure 3.3.2.: Electric accelerating field in the plasma wakefield. (a) transversal electric field in x direction, where the laser runs to the top. (b) slice of transversal electric field from the left side at $x = 0$.

momentum causes them to overshoot. The remaining charge density oscillation, referred to as a plasma wave or a plasma wakefield [24, 2], is illustrated in figure 3.3.1. The frequency scale of this oscillation is known as the plasma frequency [23]

$$\omega_p = \sqrt{\frac{n_0 e^2}{\epsilon_0 m_e}}, \quad (3.3.1)$$

where n_0 is the ambient electron number density and ϵ_0 the permittivity of free space. The associated plasma wavelength $\lambda_p = 2\pi c/\omega_p$ in practical units is given by

$$\lambda_p[\mu\text{m}] \approx 3.3 \cdot 10^{10} / \sqrt{n_0[\text{cm}^{-3}]}. \quad (3.3.2)$$

This allows to estimate the size of the positive cavity behind the laser, the so-called bubble, with $\lambda_p/2$. The displacement of the electrons from their initial position locally breaks the quasi-neutrality of the plasma. The resulting plasma wave can sustain an electric field in excess of [8]

$$E_0 = c m_e \frac{\omega_p}{e}. \quad (3.3.3)$$

By inserting the constants the formula becomes $E_0[\text{V/m}] \approx 96\sqrt{n_0[\text{cm}^{-3}]}$ and the square root dependency of E_0 on n_0 becomes obvious. This shows that a larger acceleration gradient can be achieved using a higher density. For a plasma density of $n_0 = 8 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and a laser wavelength of 800 nm, the maximum accelerating

Figure 3.3.3.: (a) Linear wake field with a laser strength parameter $a_0 = 1$,
(b) non-linear wake field with $a_0 = 4.5$.

field is $E_0 \approx 270$ GV/m. However, the critical density must not be exceeded, as otherwise, the plasma will no longer be transparent to the laser. For example, a laser wavelength of 800 nm leads to a critical density of $n_c \approx 1.7 \cdot 10^{21}$ cm⁻³ which is reached at $\omega_L = \omega_p$.

For a constant density profile one can assume that the phase velocity of the plasma wave is the same as the group velocity of the driving laser. If one considers an electron in the rear half of the bubble, it is accelerated by the electric field towards the center, whereby its speed will approach that of light, $v_e \rightarrow c$. For a constant plasma phase velocity with $v_{ph} < c$, the electrons will eventually overshoot the center of the plasma wave and decelerate. This is because the electric field decreases linearly towards the center, where it begins to rise again in the opposite direction (see figure 3.3.2). The length an electron must travel before it starts to decelerate is referred to as the dephasing length [8]

$$L_{dephasing} \approx \frac{\lambda_p^3}{\lambda_0^2} \begin{cases} \sqrt{2}a_0/\pi N_p & : a_0 \gg 1 \\ 1 & : a_0 \ll 1 \end{cases}, \quad (3.3.4)$$

where N_p denotes the number of plasma periods behind the driving pulse.

If there are many electrons in the bubble, they can deform the bubble due to their space charge. This effect is called beam loading [25]. Furthermore, the plasma dynamics depend on the laser strength parameter a_0 . Low intensities ($a_0 < 1$) drive linear plasma wakefields with $\Delta n_e/n_e \gg 1$. Figure 3.3.3 compares this linear regime to the relativistic regime ($a_0 > 1$) that is characterized by highly nonlinear dynamics. With further increasing laser intensity, the amplitude of the plasma wave begins to increase so much that the plasma dynamics can no longer be

described by linear waves and wave breaking can occur.

3.4. Wave breaking

For sufficiently large intensities and short laser pulses ($c \cdot \tau_L < \lambda_p$), the plasma density oscillation can be driven to such high amplitudes that the wake wave undergoes a transverse wave breaking. This results in the injection of electrons [26] and occurs when the length of an excursion of oscillating electrons, becomes greater than the plasma wavelength [27]. The plasma electron approach and exceed the phase velocity of the wave. Then the maximum amplitude of a nonlinear plasma wave exceeds the cold nonrelativistic wave breaking field $E_0 = c m_e \omega_p / e$ [28]. In one dimension, the maximum amplitude of a periodic plasma wave is [8]

$$E_{WB} = \sqrt{2(\gamma_p - 1)} E_0, \quad (3.4.1)$$

where $\gamma_p = (1 - v_p^2/c^2)^{-1/2} \approx \omega/\omega_p$ is the relativistic Lorentz factor associated with the phase velocity of the plasma wave. With $E_{WB} = c m_e \omega_p a_0 / e$ follows for the laser strength parameter a_0

$$a_0 = E_{WB}/E_0 = \sqrt{2(\gamma_p - 1)} \quad (3.4.2)$$

$$\Rightarrow a_0 \approx \sqrt{2(\omega/\omega_p - 1)}. \quad (3.4.3)$$

Using $\omega_p = \sqrt{\frac{n_p e^2}{\epsilon_0 m_e}}$ and $\omega = 2\pi c/\lambda$ the laser strength parameter a_0 can be written as

$$a_0 \approx \sqrt{\frac{4\pi c}{\lambda} \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon_0 m_e}{n_p e^2}} - 2} \quad (3.4.4)$$

$$\Rightarrow a_0 \approx \sqrt{\frac{66.778}{\lambda[\mu\text{m}] \sqrt{n_p[\text{m}^{-3}]}} - 2}. \quad (3.4.5)$$

As an example, for a laser wavelength $\lambda = 0.8 \mu\text{m}$ and a plasma density $n_p = 4 \cdot 10^{24} \text{m}^{-3}$ wave breaking requires $a_0 \geq 6.3$.

The mechanism described above is referred to as self-injection [26]. With self-injection through wave breaking the first quasi-monoenergetic bunches of highly relativistic electrons were observed in 2004 [29, 30, 31]. In order to be able to use the electron bunches for applications such as for synchrotron and FEL light sources, higher beam quality requirements must be achieved.

Figure 3.5.1.: Schematic drawing of an undulator. 1: magnets, 2: electron beam entering from the upper left, 3: synchrotron radiation exiting to the lower right. Graphic based on [34]

3.5. Applications

The range of applications can mainly be divided into particle accelerators and compact light sources. The latter, for example, are powerful tools for time-resolved studies of molecular and atomic dynamics. Currently, accelerator technology is limited by the pulse duration of synchrotron sources to just under a picosecond and demands large and expensive conventional accelerators. Laser-wakefield-based facilities made enormous progress in improving beam quality and stability, what makes them serious candidates for a new type of compact light sources [32]. Already 10 years ago radiation has been generated at visible [32] and soft-X-ray wavelengths [33] by passing laser-accelerated electrons through magnetic undulators which is an arrangement of magnets with an alternating transverse magnetic field. As the electrons pass through the undulator they are forced on a sinusoidal trajectory under the action of the Lorentz force of the periodic magnetic field and emit polarized radiation (figure 3.5.1). The wavelength of the emitted light λ_r depends mainly on the undulator period λ_u and the electron bunch energy by [35]

$$\lambda_r \propto \frac{\lambda_u}{2\gamma^2}, \quad (3.5.1)$$

where γ is the Lorentz factor of the electron beam. Thus electron bunches with higher energies are required to obtain emitted light at higher frequencies.

The undulator is used, for example, for a free electron laser (FEL) in order to produce bright X-rays. If the laser-accelerated electrons propagate through an undulator, they shape into microbunches separated by the resonance wavelength of

the magnetic structure as it propagates into the undulator. The term micro bunching refers to the grouping of electrons into small bunches which are separated by a fixed distance. The coherent emission of all microbunches has a wavelength equal to the periodic length between the microbunches and results in a burst of bright X-rays [36, 3]. However, there are extremely high requirements on an electron beam to be used for an XFEL or at least to produce X-ray synchrotron light. Among them, the charge should be contained within 0.1 % energy spread and 1 nC at 1 GeV will be required to produce an efficient XFEL [3].

A laser plasma accelerator also emits bright radiation as a result of the oscillation of the accelerates electron bunch in the transverse electric field of the plasma wave [32]. This behaviour is called betatron oscillation and generates incoherent radiation in the direction of the bunch motion at a very short wavelength [2, 3]. Furthermore, in the long term, plasma accelerators could be used in particle colliders. The possible accelerating gradient of more than ≈ 100 GV/m that has been obtained in LWFA promises shorter and cheaper accelerators than the conventional ones [37]. However, producing particle beams with quality comparable to that produced by conventional accelerators remains a challenge.

3.6. Beam parameter

In order to be able to use a particle beam for various applications, the beam quality must be as good as possible. To determine the electron beam quality after a laser plasma acceleration, it is necessary to find some parameters that represent the whole particle beam. To learn more about the collective motion of the particles it is convenient to observe the particles as points in six-dimensional phase space. The distribution of the particles in the phase space results from the Boltzmann equation [23]

$$\frac{\partial f(\vec{r}, \vec{v}, t)}{\partial t} + \vec{v} \cdot \nabla f(\vec{r}, \vec{v}, t) + \frac{\vec{F}}{m} \cdot \frac{\partial f(\vec{r}, \vec{v}, t)}{\partial \vec{v}} = \left(\frac{\partial f(\vec{r}, \vec{v}, t)}{\partial t} \right)_{coll} \quad (3.6.1)$$

In this context, $\vec{F}(\vec{r}, t)$ is the force field acting on the particles with the mass m . The term on the left hand side gives the total time derivative of the distribution density $f(\vec{r}, \vec{v}, t)$ and on the right hand side $\left(\frac{\partial f(\vec{r}, \vec{v}, t)}{\partial t} \right)_{coll}$ is the time rate of change of $f(\vec{r}, \vec{v}, t)$ due to collisions. If the latter is zero the particle collisions can be neglected. If the force \vec{F} is entirely electromagnetic, the collisionless Boltzmann equation is

Figure 3.6.1.: Shows the occupied area of an electron bunch transversal phase space. In order to select only the particles of the bunches, an energy filter was used.

called the Vlasov equation and takes the form [23]

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial t} + \vec{v} \cdot \nabla f + \frac{q}{m} (\vec{E} + \vec{v} \times \vec{B}) \cdot \frac{\partial f}{\partial \vec{v}} = 0 \quad (3.6.2)$$

Furthermore, the evolution of the spatial and momentum boundaries of the beam, i.e. the beam envelope, is of interest. The description of the boundary of a continuous distribution is not necessarily unique. Thus one possible definition is given by the root-mean-square (rms) envelope of a beam distribution. The rms formalism has the additional benefit of allowing a concise definition of the beam emittance which represents the effective area occupied by the beam particles in the phase space [38].

Emittance

The emittance is a measure for the extent of a particle beam in position-and-momentum phase space with regard to the root-mean-square (rms) envelope. Thus, it describes how tightly the electron beam can be focused. For applications such as synchrotron light sources, a low emittance beam is necessary to achieve high luminosity and high brightness [39]. The emittance can be independently defined in all spatial dimensions (as the volume occupied in phase space). As this thesis concentrates on the transversal emittance, figure 3.6.1 shows a transversal phase space of an electron bunch after acceleration. To describe the area occupied by the particle distribution in phase space, an ellipse is used as a contour

Figure 3.6.2.: Rms phase space ellipse that corresponds to the $\exp[-1/2]$ intensity contour. The area of the ellipse stays constant under the influence of conservative forces, which for example can cause a rotation of the ellipse.

of constant probability density. Besides choosing an ellipse that describes the half-intensity contour or an ellipse based on an enclosed fraction (e.g. 90 %) of the beam, the most useful choice is the rms phase space ellipse [38]. The rms phase space ellipse corresponds to the $\exp[-1/2]$ intensity contour and in this case, is described by the expression

$$\frac{x^2}{\sigma_x^2} + \frac{p_x^2}{\sigma_{p_x}^2} = 1, \quad (3.6.3)$$

where σ_x and σ_{p_x} are the variances of the space coordinate x and momentum coordinate p_x and correspond to the major and minor semiaxes of the ellipse (see fig. 3.6.2). Thus the phase space inside the ellipse is given by $A = \pi \sigma_x \sigma_{p_x}$ what can be written as $A = \pi \epsilon_x$. Therefore, the emittance corresponding to the rms phase space ellipse is $\epsilon_x = \sigma_x \sigma_{p_x}$. The ellipse can now be transformed by a simple drift or for example, the beam can be focused by electron beam lenses, reducing its size in one transverse dimension while increasing its angular momentum spread. But the area of the ellipse and thus the emittance stays conserved. This is a result of Liouville's theorem. It describes the time evolution of the phase space distribution function and states that under the influence of conservative forces the particle density in phase space remains constant [38, 40]. This transformation of the phase space ellipse can be described by the application of the transport matrix \mathbf{M} which can be written compactly as

$$\sigma_f = \mathbf{M} \cdot \sigma_0 \cdot \mathbf{M}^T. \quad (3.6.4)$$

Here σ_f and σ_0 represents the matrix of the variances σ_x and σ_{p_x} before as well as after the transformation and is defined as

$$\sigma \equiv \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x & \sigma_{xp_x} \\ \sigma_{p_x x} & \sigma_{p_x} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3.6.5)$$

With equation 3.6.4 and $\sigma_{xp_x} = \sigma_{p_x x}$ follows that the σ -matrix must have an invariant determinant

$$\det(\sigma) = \sigma_x \sigma_{p_x} - \sigma_{xp_x}^2 = \langle x^2 \rangle \langle p_x^2 \rangle - \langle xp_x \rangle^2 = \text{constant}. \quad (3.6.6)$$

Here the expression $\langle \dots \rangle$ denotes the expectation value of the variable in between the brackets. This constant is related to the emittance through

$$\epsilon_x^2 \equiv \det(\sigma) = \langle x^2 \rangle \langle p_x^2 \rangle - \langle xp_x \rangle^2. \quad (3.6.7)$$

This can be verified for the equilibrium case when $\langle xp_x \rangle^2 = 0$ and where the area of the rms ellipse can be written as $\pi \sqrt{\langle x^2 \rangle \langle p_x^2 \rangle} = \pi \sigma_x \sigma_{p_x}$. For a more detailed derivation see [38].

Thus the rms-emittance $\epsilon_{x,rms}$ can be written as

$$\epsilon_{x,rms} = \sqrt{\langle x^2 \rangle \langle p_x^2 \rangle - \langle xp_x \rangle^2}. \quad (3.6.8)$$

In order to compare the beam quality of different sources it is common to use the emittance normalized $\epsilon_{x,n}$ to same momentum

$$\epsilon_{x,n} = (\beta\gamma)^2 \sqrt{\langle x^2 \rangle \langle p_x^2 \rangle - \langle xp_x \rangle^2}. \quad (3.6.9)$$

The rms emittance of the full beam is also called projected emittance. For applications such as FELs, besides the projected emittance, the slice emittance is also important. Due to the slippage effect in the undulator the interaction between the electrons is limited to within the cooperation length, which is much shorter than the electron bunch length [41]. Therefore it is convenient to separate the bunch into slices and define the slice emittance $\epsilon_{x,slice}$ for this part of the bunch. Here the formula for the slice emittance $\epsilon_{x,slice}$ remains the same as for the normalized rms emittance. Furthermore individual slices may have the same (slice) emittance but if the slice rms ellipses are not concentric the emittance of the whole beam (projected emittance) is larger. This is illustrated in figure 3.6.3.

Beam energy, energy spread and charge

Other important parameters that describe the electron beam are the beam energy, energy spread and charge. These parameters can be defined in different ways.

Figure 3.6.3.: Comparison of the projected emittance (orange) and the emittance of different slices (blue). Left: bunch in direction of motion y , right: phase space ellipses.

In this thesis, for their calculation, the maximum of the quasi-monoenergetic electron bunches is first determined. In the simulations carried out in chapter 5 this corresponds to the maximum in the energy histogram (see figure 3.6.4), whereby only the energy values greater than 45 MeV are considered. Starting from this, analogous to the full width at half max (FWHM), the "full width at $1/3$ max" ($FW^{1/3M}$) limits are determined. The difference of these limits in the energy histogram is thus the energy spread. The bunch energy in turn defines itself for this thesis through the weighted average of the energies between these boundaries. In order to obtain the charge of the electron bunch, the particles within the energy spread are accumulated and multiplied by the elementary charge. As can be seen in figure 3.6.4, the $FW^{1/3M}$ compensates the local fluctuations better than the FWHM and thus provides the more stable results for this thesis.

3.7. Down-ramp injection

Since the quality of the electron beam, such as low energy spread, high energy, low emittance, is significantly determined by the injection process, it is important to be able to control the injection. In chapter 3.4 self-injection through wave breaking is introduced. Even though many experiments operate in this regime and have shown increasing stability, self-injection remains difficult to control and is inappropriate for fine-tuning or controlling electron bunches injection. Other methods for controlled injection of electrons into plasma wakefields use for example colliding laser pulses [42], ionization injection [43, 44] or injection in

Figure 3.6.4.: Energy histogram that shows the construction of the bunch energy, energy spread and charge. It also demonstrates the necessity of constructing an energy spread over "1/3" limits compared to FWHM limits in the present case.

density down-ramps [45, 46]. The present thesis focuses on down-ramp injections. Injection realized with a negative density gradient was first proposed by Bulanov in 1998 [47] and relies on the slowing down of the plasma wave velocity at the down-ramp. For LWFA based on self-injection electron injection is achieved by driving the plasma density oscillation to such high amplitude that wave breaking occurs. In contrast, density down-ramp injection exploits the gradually increasing plasma wavelength in the down-ramp and the thus reduced phase velocity of the plasma density wave [26]. This can be observed from the equation of the phase velocity [48]

$$v_p = c \left(1 + \frac{\zeta}{2n_p} \frac{dn_e}{dy} \right)^{-1}, \quad (3.7.1)$$

with $\zeta = y - ct$. For a downward density ramp, $dn_e/dy < 0$ and behind the pulse, $\zeta < 0$, the wakefield phase velocity slows down. The decrease of v_p leads to the frequency of oscillation of the electrons forming the wake being different at different locations. The oscillation of adjacent electrons eventually become antiphase and wave breaking occurs [27]. Here the minimum energy an electron needs to be trapped in a wakefield of amplitude $\Delta\phi$ is given by

$$\gamma_{min} = \gamma_p (1 + \gamma_p \Delta\phi) - \sqrt{\gamma_p^2 - 1} \sqrt{(1 + \gamma_p \Delta\phi)^2 - 1}, \quad (3.7.2)$$

Figure 3.7.1.: density profile with the position in the y-direction (propagation direction of the laser) on the x-axis and the density, related to the maximum density on the y-axis. Where (1) is the up-ramp, (2) is the high density plateau, (3) is the down-ramp with the length Δx , (4) is the lower density plateau and (5) is the down-ramp leading into the vacuum.

where $\gamma_p = (1 - v_p^2/c^2)^{-1/2}$ is the Lorentz factor related to the phase velocity of the plasma wave. For a given amplitude $\Delta\phi$, the threshold for trapping decreases as γ_p decreases. Thus it can be assumed that with density down-ramps the wave breaking threshold can be reached at sufficiently high amplitudes. Furthermore, this method enables the wave breaking to be triggered in a localized spatial region of the plasma. Figure 3.7.1 shows a typical density profile which provides an impression of a density down-ramp. This injection scheme can be divided into two regimes regarding the length of the down-ramp. Short density ramps are of the order of the plasma wavelength λ_p and have been produced experimentally for example by shock waves in gas jets [49, 50]. Compared to longer down-ramps the injection point is well-localized and therefore electron bunches with peak energy spectra can be produced [26]. Long density ramps ($> \lambda_p$) are for example applied in [51, 52] and have a long injection process which leads to an initial broad energy spectrum. However, during the further acceleration, the energy spectra can become peaked [26] and the wave breaking produces a stronger singularity of the electron density which leads to a larger number of electrons involved in the breaking [27]. Therefore it is important to know the optimal length for the down-ramp to achieve best beam parameters.

4. Simulation

As a result of the nonlinearity of the laser-plasma interaction, it is challenging to analytically study an optimal setup to reach high beam quality. This makes simulations the only feasible way to predict the complex plasma dynamics. Thereby, the study of plasma-based acceleration depends on several parameters, for example the plasma density and profile or the wavelength, pulse duration, intensity and focus position of the laser.

Because in experiments it is not possible to determine parameters exactly, it is necessary to simulate a parameter range to compare them with experiment. For example, the laser strength parameter a_0 cannot be set exactly. Therefore it is convenient to test several possible values in a simulation for comparability. If one now starts from several parameters with experimental uncertainties, one easily reaches a large number of parameter sets that need to be tested and simulated. Furthermore, due to the nonlinearity, several parameters have to be varied during the search for an optimal parameter set. Also in this scenario, a large number of simulations can be easily achieved. For example, if three parameters are varied by five different values, 125 simulations need to be performed. Thus large parameter surveys or systematic studies are desired for predicting optimized parameters, supporting experimental results and performing sensitivity analyses.

In order to be able to handle many simulations and thus a lot of data, a fast code is required. One of the most performant codes for particles in cell (PIC) simulations is PConGPU [53].

4.1. Particle-in-cell simulations

The fundamental principles of the particle-in-cell (PIC) simulation were already laid out in 1983 by Dawson [12], who was also one of the pioneers of laser-driven plasma-based accelerators [7]. The PIC algorithm is a tool in computational plasma physics that computes the movement of particles in electromagnetic fields. It becomes essential especially if the dynamics of the plasma constituents cannot be described by ensemble-averaged variables such as density or temperature, as it is done in the magneto hydro dynamics (MHD) approach. However, the simulation of every single particle motion and their particle-particle interaction is not feasible for large systems. In order to make simulations at all possible, the PIC-algorithm uses macroparticles and a mean field approach to overcome this issue. A macroparticle is a computational particle that represents many real particles and carries a charge q and a mass m [54]. They are defined by a particle density distribution function to describe the dynamics of the represented single particles. The individual particles are assumed to follow the same trajectory as the associated macroparticle and can therefore be represented by them, since the Lorentz force depends only on the charge-to-mass ratio. Moreover, the simulation volume is partitioned into a grid (cells) while maintaining the particles as freely moving entities [55]. The electric and magnetic fields are interpolated on this physical grid. This allows the PIC algorithm to solve the Maxwell-Vlasov system of equation 4.1.1-4.1.6 that can be used to describe the charged components of the plasma. In this equation the different species of particles constituting the plasma are described by their distribution function $f_s(\vec{r}, \vec{v}, t)$, where s denotes the species of the particle. The distribution function f_s satisfies the Vlasov's equation 4.1.1 (see chapter 3.6, equation 3.6.2). It contains the Lorentz force \vec{F}_L (eq. 4.1.2) that acts on the particles

$$\frac{\partial f_s(\vec{r}, \vec{v}, t)}{\partial t} + \vec{v} \cdot \nabla f_s(\vec{r}, \vec{v}, t) + \frac{\vec{F}_L}{m_s} \cdot \frac{\partial f_s(\vec{r}, \vec{v}, t)}{\partial \vec{v}} = 0 \quad (4.1.1)$$

$$\vec{F}_L = q_s(\vec{E} + \vec{v} \times \vec{B}), \quad (4.1.2)$$

where the Lorentz force follows from the \vec{E} - and \vec{B} - fields that satisfy Maxwell's equation (4.1.3-4.1.6).

Figure 4.1.1.: Cycle of the particle-in-cell algorithm

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{E} = \frac{\rho}{\epsilon_0} \quad (4.1.3)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{B} = 0 \quad (4.1.4)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{E} = -\frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t} \quad (4.1.5)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{B} = \mu_0 \vec{j} + \mu_0 \epsilon_0 \frac{\partial \vec{E}}{\partial t} \quad (4.1.6)$$

The actual simulation runs through discrete time steps where each step involves four phases as illustrated in figure 4.1.1. Starting with a given electric and magnetic field (figure 4.1.1 bottom left), resolved on the grid points¹ and the macroparticles between them as shown in figure 4.1.2. From this, the Lorentz force, that acts on each macroparticle, can be calculated (figure 4.1.1 top left). In this step the particles are only influenced by the fields on the surrounding grid points. Therefore, the algorithm only acts on the local values in the simulation domain, which reduces simulation time. Next, the macroparticles are moved due to this force and their change in position and momentum can be computed by solving the equation of motion. This step is usually called the particle pusher (figure 4.1.1 top right). There are different algorithms that can be used to implement the particle pusher. Two common schemes were proposed by Boris [57] and Vay [58]. The next step computes the current that is induced by the movement of the particles (figure 4.1.1 bottom right). Following Ampère's law (equation 4.1.6), these currents

¹A detailed description of the grid points can be found in [56]

Figure 4.1.2.: Spatial distribution of particles inside a discrete grid of the cells with electric and magnetic fields distributed on the grid, as assumed by the PIC algorithm.

create magnetic fields. These magnetic fields, in turn, create electric fields as described by Faraday's law (equation 4.1.5). With this, the fields can be updated by superimposing the changes of the fields onto the fields on the grid. Then they can act on the particles again and the cycle can start over. The advantage that Graphical Processing Units (GPUs) are much faster in massively parallel jobs than CPUs, allows large-scale PIC simulations on GPU clusters in an acceptable time. The first PIC algorithm that is completely implemented on scalable GPU clusters is PIConGPU [54].

4.2. PIConGPU

Particle-in-cell on Graphical Processing Units (PIConGPU) is an open-source implementation of the fully relativistic PIC algorithm for GPUs. It enables the parallelization of the PIC algorithm on many-core systems in order to simulate three-dimensional field-particle interaction with high spatial resolution. It was started at the HZDR in cooperation with the Centre for Information Services and High-Performance Computing (ZIH) of the TU Dresden and has been continuously developed at the HZDR. PIConGPU can perform the numerical calculations on scalable GPU cluster which results in considerable performance advantage compared to conventional computing on CPUs. Thus, for standard LWFA simulation a result cannot be expected in weeks, but in less than a day, because the computing

Figure 4.2.1.: Left: The Simulation domain is decomposed into subdomains that are managed each by a GPU. Every subdomain consists of supercells, which in turn are subdivided into cells. Right: Each subdomain is composed of (white) a core and (orange) a border.

performance on GPUs is about eight times faster than on CPUs². In order to achieve the parallelism with complete calculation on GPUs, data localization is required. This is obtained by domain decomposition of particle and field data.

Domain Decomposition

Domain decomposition is a beneficial technique for particle-mesh computation. It defines the division of the global simulation domain into a collection of cells. The cells within a cuboid volume are grouped into supercells. In PIConGPU a supercell is mapped to a block that is a group of threads, for PIConGPU typically one block contains 256 threads. A thread is the smallest sequence that performs calculations. Here a thread is responsible for the calculations of one field or one particle of a cell. Several of the supercells, in turn, form a cuboid volume, which defines the local simulation domain of a single GPU [60] as shown in figure 4.2.1 on the left site. The global memory can be accessed by all threads, while all threads belonging to the same block can exchange data via the temporary and faster memory, which is called shared memory.

The particles can move in each iteration not only within the cell but also beyond the borders of a cell [61]. Thus the particles are able to move through the cells and interact with the fields making PIC a particle mesh algorithm [62]. Also for the calculation of the magnetic field and current, data from the neighbouring cells is needed. This leads to an interleaving of calculations on the GPU and data exchange in the border area of the subdomains. For this purpose, the cells within a

² GPU/CPU Flop/s on Hypnos k20 queue = 7.6 : 1 [59]

subdomain, that is managed by one GPU, are divided into two regions. On the one hand, the area in which the subdomains are adjacent to each other, the "border", and on the other hand the remaining area in between, the "core" (see figure right 4.2.1). With the PIC algorithm relying on local field updates on the grid points, the fields for the core and the border can be computed independently. Then the data can be exchanged between GPUS at the boundaries without affecting the calculations on the core [54]. This increases the computational performance of PIConGPU.

4.3. Visualization of simulation data

For the evaluation and visualization of simulations, for example, HDF5 data can be used, which can be generated by PIConGPU during a simulation. Here **HDF5** is the *Hierarchical Data Format* [63, 64] that is a file format designed to store and organize large amounts of data. It simplifies the file structure to include datasets, which are multidimensional arrays and groups which are container structures that can hold datasets and other groups. This results in a hierarchical, filesystem-like data format. In case of PIConGPU, it stores simulation data such as fields and particles along with meta data such as conversion factors. The HDF5 data can be used for post-simulation analysis and for restarting a simulation after a crash. The specific internal standard to structure physical quantities used for HDF5 is called **openPMD** which stands for *open standard for particle-mesh data files* [65]. This standard includes meta data and naming schemes that allows exchanging particle and mesh-based data from a scientific simulation. It can be used for a unified description of post-processing, visualisation and analysis.

openPMD-viewer

The simulation data stored in the HDF5 format with the openPMD standard can then be loaded and visualized with the openPMD-viewer [66]. It provides a Python API that for example converts units correctly to SI, interprets iteration steps of the simulation and annotates axes. This API can be used to write a script that loads the data and produces a set of pre-defined plots. Moreover, it provides an interactive GUI that can be used inside a Jupyter Notebook in order to interactively visualize the data. For example, it is possible to visualize the charge density, electric and magnetic fields in space, or the longitudinal and transverse phase space.

Figure 4.3.1.: Depicts the Jupyter post-processing interface that allows to interactively filter and visualize HDF5 data.

Jupyter Notebook

The Jupyter Notebook [67] is an open-source web application that eases the process to create and share documents that contain live code, equations, visualizations and narrative text. It was developed as a document format to publish code, results and explanations which are both readable and executable. The notebooks also supports the workflow of scientific computing. Therefore the code in a notebook is organised into cells, which can be individually modified and executed. The output from each cell appears directly below it and is stored as part of the document. Furthermore, the jupyter notebook supports interactive widgets, which are eventful python objects that have a representation in the browser [68]. They can be used to build an interactive GUI for notebooks. For example with the slider widget, a variable can be set by sliding a controller. Other widgets are buttons, dropdowns or checkboxes.

Figure 4.3.2.: (a) energy waterfall histogram generated by evaluating HDF5 data. (b) energy waterfall histogram generated with a plugin.

Jupyter post-processing interface

In order to be able to filter the simulation data interactively and to display further derived quantities, the author has developed another post-processing tool for this purpose. Figure 4.3.1 shows the interface of this tool. With it, an energy histogram as well as an energy waterfall histogram, the transverse and the longitudinal phase space, the evolution of the transverse emittance and slice emittance over all iteration steps, the electric and magnetic field, the electron density, the transverse Lorentz force and the potential of the longitudinal electric field for interactively filtered simulation data can be displayed.

In order to start the visualization, the path to the simulation as well as the particle species to be analysed, are set and the iteration step of the simulation is selected via a slider. In the following, filters can be selected and their limits can be adjusted by sliders. Here, it is possible to choose between filters for energy, transversal and longitudinal spatial direction and transversal impulses. For this, it is optional to select a filter or to combine several filters. For the gamma filter the momentum p_x and weighting w are taken from the HDF5 data to determine first u_x , u_y and u_z and thus gamma using:

$$u_x = \frac{p_x \cdot \text{Unit}_{SI}}{w \cdot c \cdot m_e} \quad (4.3.1)$$

$$\gamma = \left(\sqrt{u_x^2 + u_y^2 + u_z^2} + 1 \right) \quad (4.3.2)$$

The slider for the gamma filter sets the upper and lower limit of the requested gamma range. The position filter can be used to select the range in which the particles are allowed to stay locally. The last filter uses the momentum from the

Figure 4.3.3.: Left: two-dimensional plot of the Lorentz force. Right: Lorentz force depending on the z position on the y -slices marked on the left. Here you can see for the case of the non-linear regime that the Lorentz force increases linearly and changes its sign in the middle.

HDF5 data to select the particles that have a momentum in the desired range. In the following, one or more graphs can be selected to visualize the data. The values for the energy histogram, the phase space diagrams, the electric and magnetic field and the charge density are calculated and displayed analogously to the openPMD viewer. In addition, the correctness of the generated visualizations was ensured by comparing with the openPMD viewer.

The energy waterfall histogram represents the timewise evolution of the individual energy histograms of a simulation by putting the individual histograms for each time step in a row as a two-dimensional histogram (see figure 4.3.2).

The resulting energy waterfall histogram was compared with the Energy Histogram plugin to ensure its correctness. As will be discussed later this section, the comparison already shows that a much better resolution can be achieved with the plugin than with the evaluation of the HDF5 data.

For the visualization of the transversal Lorentz force on a relativistic electron propagating along the y -direction (see figure 4.3.3), the transversal electric and magnetic field from the HDF5 data is used as:

$$F_L = (E_z - c B_x) \quad (4.3.3)$$

In order to show the development of the emittance and the slice emittance (see

Figure 4.3.4.: (a) Evolution of the projected emittance. (b) Evolution of the slice emittance (blue) and the number of particles (green) for each timestep.

figure 4.3.4), for example, the normalized emittance in x-direction was calculated analogous to equation 3.6.9 using:

$$\epsilon_x^n = \sqrt{\langle x^2 \rangle \langle u_x^2 \rangle - \langle x u_x \rangle^2}. \quad (4.3.4)$$

In order to ensure the correctness, several values of the emittance were compared with the openPMD viewer, which can output the emittance value for a fixed time step, but does not plot the course over several time steps.

Motivation of in-situ analyses

However, writing HDF5 data during simulation takes a lot of time and memory. For an exemplary simulation similar to the ones described in section 5.1 the writing of HDF5 data needs 662 GB of memory and 159 min of simulation time. Even reading this 662 GB takes 44min at hypnos, the largest cluster at HZDR, that can read files at about 250 MB/s if reading is distributed over several nodes. Writing data or performing calculations as it is done in post-processing is even slower.

In contrast, the Nvidia K20 GPUs of the hypnos k20 queue can perform calculations with 3.52 TFLOPS and have a memory bandwidth of up to 208 GB/s [69]. The

speed at which the data can be read is already reduced to a quarter by the transfer of the data to the CPUs, since the CPUs in the hypnos cluster have a bandwidth to the RAM of approximately 50 GB/s. After saving the data on the filesystem the speed is again reduced by a factor 200. Thus the access of the data from the filesystem is at least 800 times slower than a direct calculation on the GPU would be. This makes it necessary to perform the analyses already during the simulation on the GPU level. Here the particles can be analyzed massively parallel and at the same time profit from the high processing speed of the GPUs. This method is called in-situ analysis and implemented by so-called plugins. Thus the storage space of the above-mentioned simulation can be reduced to less than 10 GB and also the simulation time is reduced to 108min, because the field and particle data no longer have to be stored for each timestep but only single calculated quantities. Thus only 1.5 % of the memory and only 68 % of the simulation time are needed when using plugins instead of writing HDF5 data. Furthermore, a much better resolution of the plots can be achieved with a plugin, because it allows the evaluation of the data more frequently. A comparison can be seen in figure 4.3.2, which compares the energy evolution histogram generated with HDF5 data and the one generated with a plugin. Therefore the author developed a plugin which calculates the projected transversal emittance and slice emittance (see chapter 4.4).

Comparison of post-processing and in-situ analysis

However, if one goes over to an exclusive use of plugins without generating HDF5 data, calculations in post-processing become difficult or even impossible. Among other things, with the help of HDF5 data the particles can be filtered in post-processing, e.g. according to their energies, in order to evaluate only particles above a certain threshold energy. Such filters can also be defined for the simulation and thus for the plugin, but in contrast to post-processing, they can not be adjusted afterwards. Thus, the planned analyses and settings must be known in advance of the simulation. But in addition to saving simulation time and storage space as well as increasing the plot resolution, plugins also have more advantages. For example the checkpoint plugin allows to create checkpoints from which simulations can be restarted for instance in case of a crash. Furthermore, due to the savings in simulation time and memory in in-situ analyses, considerably more simulations can be started in one scan and thus explorative scientific simulations are enabled. This makes online analyses possible, in which simulations can simply

be started and subsequently evaluated. Such a tool, in the development of which the author was involved, is described in chapter 4.5.

Therefore post-processing tools like the openPMD viewer can be used to view individual simulation results. But with increasing size of the simulations, with a larger number of simulations or for online analyses plugins are inevitable. Thus the use of in-situ analyses speeds up and simplifies the evaluation of simulations with a better resolution and accuracy in contrast to the post-processing of already reduced but still large data sets.

4.4. Emittance plugin

As part of this master thesis, an emittance plugin, which is a massively parallel in-situ analysis, was implemented in PIConGPU. As discussed in chapter 3.6, the emittance describes how tightly the electron beam is concentrated in phase space. Since this is an important parameter for synchrotron light sources, it is interesting to determine the emittance. The emittance plugin calculates the normalized projected emittance in the x-direction for each time step. Furthermore, the y-axis of the simulation box is divided into slices and the normalized transversal slice emittance in the x-direction is calculated for these.

For the visualization of these emittance values, different classes were written by the author. With the `emittance_evolution_visualizer` the emittance is plotted for each time step, as shown in figure 4.4.1 (a). This describes how the emittance changes during the simulation process and thus helps to understand when an emittance increases or decreases. The slice emittance at a fixed time step for all slices of the simulation box is plotted with the `slice_emittance_visualizer` (see figure 4.4.1 (b)). With the `slice_emittance_waterfall_visualizer` this slice emittance can be displayed over all time steps as shown in figure 4.4.1 (c).

Implementation

The user of the emittance plugin can decide with which temporal resolution, i.e. how often, the emittance should be determined. For this purpose, it can be specified at how many time steps the emittance plugin is executed. During a time step, it is called and executed within the PIC cycles. The massively parallel calculation of the emittance starts with the kernel, where the shared memory is created at the beginning. In order to calculate the emittance, the position and momentum of

Figure 4.4.1.: (a) Depicts the evolution of the emittance with the time on the x-axis and the corresponding emittance value on the y-axis, (b) slice emittance for one timestep with the left edge of each slice on the x-axis and the corresponding slice emittance value for this slice on the y-axis. (c) Presents the evolution of the slice emittance for the particles within 10 cells ($\approx 0.4 \mu\text{m}$) for each y-slice (x-axis) and time (y-axis)

each particle in a cell is determined. According to the formula 3.6.9 the products x^2 , p_x^2 , xp_x for all individual particles of this cell are formed, summed up and stored in the shared memory. The number of particles in the current cell is also determined for the later calculation of the averages. Since for the determination of the emittance the mean values have to be calculated for all particles in the requested range, these intermediate results cannot be used to calculate the emittance at this point. This is done for each cell in a supercell (see figure 4.4.2) and

after all threads in a block have completed their calculations the intermediate results x^2 , p_x^2 , xp_x with the same y-cellindex are summed up and stored in the global memory, the persistent memory of one GPU. This process is performed for all blocks simultaneously and when they have completed their calculations it is repeated for the remaining supercells. Thus the intermediate results for each supercell can be determined and summed up with respect to its y position. Since this happens simultaneously on all GPUs in the domain, the final intermediate results are obtained by a plane-reduce operation, which is shown in figure 4.4.3. This accumulates the intermediate results of the GPUs in a plane, perpendicular to the direction of movement of the laser. Since the intermediate results are still on different GPUs, they are written with the MPI-gather operation on common arrays. So one gets for the products x^2 , p_x^2 , xp_x and the number of particles as array with the corresponding values per y-position. For the projected emittance each of this arrays is accumulated and finally, the emittance is calculated with:

$$\epsilon_{x,n} = \frac{\sqrt{x^2 \cdot p_x^2 - (xp_x)^2}}{N} \quad (4.4.1)$$

Figure 4.4.2.: Each thread in a block performs the calculations for one macroparticle in a cell of a supercell. Once the calculations of all blocks been completed and there are uncalculated supercells left over, this is repeated for the next supercells. This is done in parallel for all GPUs forming the calculation for the entire domain.

Figure 4.4.3.: The results of all GPUs are reduced on the transversal level and then combined on an array (Gather).

where N is the number of particles.

In order to compute the slice emittance, only the intermediate results of 10 successive y positions are added together and the emittance values for these y -slices are determined. This results in the slice emittance values for each 10th y position.

4.5. PIConGPU graphical user interface

As described at the beginning of chapter 4, large parameter surveys or systematic studies are desired for, predicting optimized parameters, supporting experimental results and perform sensitivity analysis. Due to the high computational performance and computing power of PIConGPU as well as with in-situ analyses systematic studies become possible. But starting many simulations is complex and time-consuming.

An online tool should simplify this and enable the user to start many simulations simultaneously without having UNIX command-line knowledge and knowing the structure of PIConGPU or the cluster. In the scope of this master thesis, the author was involved in the development of such a tool. It allows to change simulation parameters easily via a graphical user interface (GUI) and to start systematic studies easily on a cluster. Furthermore, simulation outputs can be visualized interactively and submitted simulations or scans can be managed.

The current appearance of this tool can be seen in figure 4.5.1 and 4.5.2. In the first tab "**Submission**" (see figure 4.5.1), single simulations as well as systematic

studies can be started and the status of started simulations can be checked. To start simulations, different simulation parameters can be selected using sliders. Here it is also possible to set an interval for parameter and the number of subdivisions for a systematic studies. The "submit" button automatically indicates how many simulations would be executed. If an already started simulation is selected, the parameters used for this simulation and its status is displayed. Currently running or compiling simulations can be aborted with a button right to scan-selection. The display of the second tab "**visualization**" (see figure 4.5.2) is divided into three columns. In each column, a scan, a corresponding simulation, and a visualizer can be selected. Depending on the visualizer, further attributes can be selected. These can be for example filters, species or coordinate directions. The currently available visualizers are listed in table 4.1.

Once the visualizer and its attributes, such as the filter, have been selected for a specific simulation, the **iteration-slider** (see figure 4.5.2) can be used to generate the visualisation at the desired iteration. Thus, the visualized quantity can be investigated interactively over time. Since this is possible for each column, different visualizations for a simulation can be compared with each other in order to understand the relevant physical processes as well as possible. Likewise, different simulations can be compared with each other. Thus the physical behaviour due to changes in different simulation parameters can be investigated very well.

Another possibility to **directly compare different simulations** from a scan is

Figure 4.5.1.: Visualization of the PIConGPU GUI, which shows the main features of the "submission-tab".

visualizer	description	attributes
energy_histogram	plots an energy histogram for one timestep	species, filter
energy_waterfall	creates a two dimensional energy histogram that represents all timesteps	species, filter
phase_space	creates a phase space diagram for one timestep	species, filter, coordinates
png	creates a picture that visualises the electron density and the laser	species, filter, coordinates
emittance_evolution	plots value of transverse emittance for each iteration	species, filter
slice_emittance	plots slice emittance for each slice for one iteration	species, filter
slice_emittance_waterfall	plots slice emittance for each slice for each iteration	species, filter
compare	plots a requested quantity (observable) depending on a selected simulation parameter (variation)	species, filter, observable, variation

Table 4.1.: Visualizers of the PIconGPU GUI.

This User Interface allows you to manage the simulation runs you have done so far by showing you some plots of the produced results. When selecting a simulation whose status is not 'compiling' anymore, you can visualize the results produced so far by clicking the 'Visualize' button. When selecting 'NEW SCAN' from the dropdown, you can also submit new simulations (make sure to first adjust the parameter sliders to the values you need). If by chance, you chose a value configuration that matches exactly one of your previous simulation runs, then no new job will be submitted. Feel free to adjust the parameters to your choice and hit 'Submit new scan' to compile and run a simulation on hypos cluster of HZDR. After a simulation has finished running, you can also download all the output data of this run as a tar-ball (*.tar.gz).

Figure 4.5.2.: Visualization of the PICongPU GUI, which shows the main features of the "visualization-tab".

the `compare_1d_visualizer`. With the attribute "variation" (see figure 4.5.2) of this visualizer the simulation parameter is chosen which has changed between the different simulations. The attribute "observable" selects between the maximum energy and the emittance³, whose values this visualizer determines for each simulation in the selected scan. Then the selected observable is plotted over the selected variation for all simulations in the scan.

As visualised in figure 4.5.3, for the construction of the content of the "submit" tab the `params.py` is accessed first. Here one can **specify the parameters** which should appear in the GUI. There its type (compile or runtime), range, default value and unit are specified. In order to set these for the PICongPU simulation, they must be set variably in the corresponding **parameter input files** (e.g. `density.param`). In order to display the simulation data in the "visualization" tab, the output data of the PICongPU simulation is parsed by a **reader class** (e.g. `compare.py`) and then displayed by the **visualizer class** (e.g. `compare_1d_visualizer`). The attributes of the visualizer are controlled by the **visualizer widgets**.

The PICongPU GUI enables parameter scans, modeling of experimental setups and sensitivity analyses. For a parameter scan, the input parameters can be varied

³The calculations of beam energy, energy spread and charge were not transferred to the GUI, because the underlying algorithms are tested and applicable for this thesis, but do not have to be generally valid.

Figure 4.5.3.: Structure of how GUI and PIConGPU are connected.

Figure 4.5.4.: Conceptual screen design for the PIConGPU GUI.

over a wide range to obtain optimum settings to achieve the best possible beam quality. In order to be able to support the results of an experiment by simulations, a systematic study is useful. For these, the settings of the experiment can be used as a basis in the GUI and the parameters can be varied by their uncertainties in order to reconstruct the actual measurements. Also a sensitivity analysis can

be performed with the GUI, in which an input parameter is varied within a small range to see what influence small fluctuations of the input parameter have on the result.

Outlook

For the development of the GUI several screen designs were created. The current template for the development is shown in figure 4.5.4. For example, it is planned that the simulations can be individually arranged in groups and that the time slider of the three columns can be linked to each other. Further visualizers for other plugins can be added. Another visualizer could also display a live visualization video or a two-dimensional compare visualizer, where an observable can be viewed over two different changed simulation parameters. It is also planned, to be able to display the energy histogram curves of several simulations simultaneously.

5. Down-ramp injection parameter scans

With the running of parameter scans the benefit and functionality of the PIConGPU GUI, the new tool for easy control of systematic studies, is demonstrated. In the regime of the density down-ramp injection the influence of the focus position of the laser, the laser strength parameter a_0 and the length of the density down-ramp Δx on the energy, energy spread and charge of the injected electron bunch as well as the maximum energy reached and the projected emittance are determined with three large parameter scans.

The parameter-scan is one of the possible applications of the PIConGPU GUI besides the sensitivity analysis as well as the simulation of the experimental setup and enables to find a set of optimal input parameters. There are two types of input parameters. On the one hand, some parameters, such as the density profile or the laser wavelength are difficult to change in an experiment. Searching for the optimum here thus greatly facilitates the design of future experiments. On the other hand, parameters such as the focus position or the laser intensity are easy to set and change in the experiment. This allows an easy comparison of the experiment with the simulation and thus a validation of the results of the parameter scans.

In the present work, the focus position of the laser is varied, which can be easily adjusted with the help of off-axis parabolas in the experiment. Furthermore, the density profile is changed by testing different lengths of the down-ramp. In order to create a density profile with a density transition in the experiment, two gas nozzles [70] can be used or the gas of one nozzle can be modified by using a razor blade [50]. This makes it very difficult to adjust the profile in a well defined

way. Usually, it requires interrupting the experiment because the razor blade position needs to be changed or the entire nozzle needs to be replaced. Especially, the new gas profil needs to be characterized and verified by diagnostics. It is therefore helpful if the optimal profile can be determined using simulations. Here the length of the down-ramp is of special interest as it directly influences the beam parameters as described in chapter 3.6. Another parameter scanned for this thesis is a_0 , which can be varied experimentally by the intensity of the laser. With the help of these scans an optimal range for the focus position is found. By varying the down-ramp length Δx , a range is determined in which the energy spread and the emittance are lower, while the energy and charge of the bunch are increased. Furthermore the influence of a_0 was investigated.

5.1. Simulation parameters

The PIconGPU GUI was used to start the parameter scans on the *hypnos* cluster at HZDR using PIconGPU (see section 4.2). The laser parameters are chosen similar to the parameters of the *Draco* laser at HZDR. Thus a laser with a Gaussian beam profile linearly polarized in the x-direction with a wavelength of $\lambda_L = 800$ nm, a FWHM spot size of $w_0 = 16$ μm at the focus position and a FWHM pulse duration of $\tau = 28$ fs are used. To observe a controlled down-ramp triggered injection, a_0 should be chosen smaller than 5.3 because from this point on self-injection is also possible (see chapter 3.4). According to [71], the matching condition for a blowout regime using a linearly polarized laser is given by

$$c \cdot \tau \lesssim w_0 \approx 2\sqrt{a_0}c/\omega_p \quad (5.1.1)$$

It describes that at a higher laser intensity and lower density, the matching spot-size increases. It also states that the pulse length ($c \cdot \tau$) must be smaller than the spotsize. For $a_0 = 4.5$ and a density of $\rho = 2.2 \cdot 10^{24} \text{ m}^{-3}$ the matching condition is satisfied. A preferably high density¹ was used since the acceleration gradient increases with the density (see section 3.3). Moreover, the pulse length ($c \cdot \tau \approx 8$ μm) is also small enough compared to the plasma length ($\lambda_p \approx 22$ μm), so that there is enough space in the bubble for the acceleration of the electron bunch without overlapping with the laser pulse. The slightly larger spot size² causes an expansion of the bubble at the place of the laser, which also enlarges the entire bubble.

¹ In order to fulfil this matching condition exactly a density of $1.94 \cdot 10^{24} \text{ m}^{-3}$ would be necessary.

² According to the matching condition, a spot size of 14.9 μm to a density of $2.2 \cdot 10^{24} \text{ m}^{-3}$ would fit best.

	first scan short focus range	second scan long focus range	third scan laser strength parameter a_0
description	variation of the focus pos. in a short range around the region of the down-ramp	variation of the focus pos. in a long range beyond the Rayleigh length of the laser	variation of the laser strength parameter a_0
focus pos.	80 – 170 μm 10 sample points	20 – 1400 μm 10 sample points	120 μm -
length of down-ramp Δx	3 – 60 μm 10 sample points	3 – 60 μm 5 sample points	3 – 60 μm 10 sample points
a_0	4.5 -	4.5 -	3 -11 15 sample points
# simulations	100	50	150

Table 5.1.: Overview of the three scans.

For the first and higher density plateau, a density ($\rho_{max} = 3.98 \cdot 10^{24} \text{ m}^{-3}$) 1.8 times as high as in the later acceleration region was applied. The density profile used is shown in figure 3.7.1. The length of the first plateau is chosen to be five periods of the plasma wave, so that the initial bubble is stable and well-defined before the system rapidly changes at the down-ramp and the injection takes place. The plasma is represented by electrons while neglecting the ion motion ($m_p = \infty$) as commonly assumed in LWFA PIC simulations.

The discretized grid spanned $384 \times 2048 \times 384$ cells with a cell size of $dy = 0.0443 \mu\text{m} \approx 0.05 \lambda_L$, $dx = dz = 0.1772 \mu\text{m} \approx 0.22 \lambda_L$ and a timestep $dt = 0.139 \text{ fs}$. For the simulations, 16 GPUs (one in x- and z-direction and 16 in the y-direction) on the K20 queue at the *hypnos* cluster at HZDR were used to compute 34000 iterations in approximately 6 h. This allows for four simulations to be carried out in parallel. Furthermore, a filter was applied to the data corresponding to the experiment, which allows only those particles which have a momentum vector within a cone of an $2 \cdot 3.8$ degrees opening angle (pinhole) and a kinetic energy larger than 5 MeV.

Based on these settings, three scans (see table 5.1) were performed using the PIconGPU GUI. For the first scan, the focus is varied between 80 μm and 170 μm and the length of the down-ramp between 3 μm and 60 μm . For this purpose,

both ranges were set in the GUI using the sliders and ten sample points. Thus, testing both parameters for ten values results in 100 simulations. As described in Chapter 5, a distinction is made between long and short down-ramps, depending on the plasma wavelength. Here, a length is chosen for the down-ramp which increases from a seventh up to three times of the plasma wavelength. The focus is varied around the region of the down-ramp since the optimal focus position is expected where the injection takes place. In a later scan, the range for the focus is expanded to $20\ \mu\text{m} - 1400\ \mu\text{m}$ with additional ten sample points, while the down-ramp length is varied between $3\ \mu\text{m}$ and $60\ \mu\text{m}$ with only five sample points. Then, another scan analyzed the influence of the laser strength parameter α_0 . Therefore α_0 is varied from 3 to 11 with 15 sample points. At the same time the length of the down-ramp is varied using ten sample points between $3\ \mu\text{m} - 60\ \mu\text{m}$. In this third scan, the focus position is set at $120\ \mu\text{m}$.

5.2. Observations

For the evaluation of the scans, the emittance, beam energy, energy spread and charge within the FWHM of the bunch (see section 3.6) are determined at the end of the simulation (iteration 34000 at approximately 1.4 mm) for each simulation and plotted over the varied simulation parameters. Depending on the question to be investigated, a different iteration could also be chosen here, for example, to investigate the influence of the acceleration region. For comparability with the experiment, the end of the simulation is chosen, which describes the state when the beam leaves the gas. Another parameter considered is the maximum energy. This quantity is defined as the highest electron energy value for which the respective charge exceeding this energy is at least 1 pC. This results in plots such as shown in figure 5.2.1, where each of the 100 pixels represents a complete simulation with its own energy spectrum and emittance. An example for the change of the energy spectra for eight pixels in the column of a plot in the third scan at $\Delta x = 3\ \mu\text{m}$ and increasing α_0 can be seen in figure 5.2.7.

First scan: short focus range

It turns out that regardless of the focus position the injection starts with the decrease of the density and stops with the end of the down-ramp. Furthermore it can be concluded that using a steeper down-ramp more electrons per micrometer

can be injected than with flatter down-ramps. A maximum injected **charge** of over 825 pC can be detected at a down-ramp length $\Delta x = 9 \mu\text{m}$, whereas for a larger $\Delta x = 60 \mu\text{m}$ the charge of the bunches is less than 650 pC. Thus for this reduction of the down-ramp length, an increase of the charge of about 27 % can be achieved (see figure 5.2.1 (d)). For very short down-ramps ($\Delta x = 3 \mu\text{m}$) the time of injection of electrons is too short to further increase the bunch charge and thus the charge of the bunches is slightly lower than for $\Delta x = 9 \mu\text{m}$. After the injection the electrons are accelerated in the constant density region of the second plateau. Figure 5.2.1 shows further the results of the first scan. It can be seen, that there is almost no influence of the **focus position** on all examined values. This is not surprising as the laser profile changes only slightly within the Rayleigh length $z_R = 883.6 \mu\text{m}$ (see section 3.1). Since only the area of the focus position around the down-ramp is considered in this scan, it was changed by $80 \mu\text{m}$, which corresponds to less than one-tenth of the Rayleigh length and thus, the focus position has nearly no influence in this range.

On the other hand, when changing the **length of the down-ramp**, the influence on all considered parameters (beam energy, energy spread, charge, maximum energy and emittance) is obvious. There is a clear increase in the **energy of the electron bunches** with decreasing down-ramp length, which can be argued with the extension of the acceleration distance for a constant simulation end and a shorter Δx . So the bunch energy for $\Delta x = 3 \mu\text{m}$ is about 178 MeV, while for $\Delta x = 60 \mu\text{m}$ it is about 158 MeV. Thus, an increase in bunch energy of 13 % is achieved by reducing the down-ramp length in the here considered range.

The **maximum energy** reached is highest with approximately 460 MeV in the case of a down-ramp of approximately $\Delta x = 16 \mu\text{m}$. For $\Delta x > 50 \mu\text{m}$ it is smaller than 400 MeV. This represents an increase of 15 %.

For the **energy spread** there is a minimum in the range of $16 \mu\text{m} < \Delta x < 35 \mu\text{m}$. Thus, the energy spread could be lowered in this range by 21 % to approximately 55 MeV, compared to the larger and smaller down-ramp length that were tested. For the **emittance**, the tendency can be seen that it is decreased in the range of $16 \mu\text{m} < \Delta x < 47 \mu\text{m}$, where it fluctuates about $165 \pi \text{ mm mrad}$.

The energy spread and the emittance are influenced by two things. On the one hand, for longer down-ramps, the electron injection in the plasma takes place in a slower manner and thus, it takes place over a longer period of time. The later injected electrons are injected further back in the expanding bubble where the higher electric field is higher (see section 3.3), while the earlier injected electrons approaching the center of the bubble where the field is weaker. Thus, a quasi-

Figure 5.2.1.: The first scan shows that for $\Delta x \approx 0.7\lambda_p$ the bunch energy, maximum energy and charge are increased while the energy spread and emittance are reduced. Furthermore it turns out that the variation of the focus position over the range of 10 % of the Rayleigh length has no influence. First scan at $a_0 = 4.5$, $\lambda_L = 800$ nm, $w_0^{FWHM} = 16$ μm, $\tau^{FWHM} = 28$ fs, $\rho_{max}/\rho = 1,8$ and $\rho_{max} = 3.98 \cdot 10^{24} m^{-3}$. Shows dependence on the length of the down-ramp Δx and focus position of (a) the bunch energy, (b) the energy spread, (c) the maximum energy, (d) the charge of the bunch and (e) the projected emittance.

Figure 5.2.2.: Left: evolution of emittance without filter. Right: evolution of emittance with pinhole (within 7.6°) and energy (> 5 MeV) filter. The segments within the density profile (see figure 3.7.1) are marked with (1) - (3): up-ramp - down-ramp, (4): lower density plateau and (5): down-ramp leading into the vacuum.

monoenergetic electron bunch can be formed [27]. On the other hand, as the Δx increases, the injection duration also increases, resulting in an energetically expanded electron bunch. If $\Delta x > 50 \mu\text{m}$, the long injection duration can no longer be balanced out by the decreasing electric field inside the bubble and thus the energy spectrum becomes wider and the emittance increases. So the quality of the electron bunch, the resulting beam energy and the maximum energy depend on how long and at which point in the wake wave the electrons are injected.

Thus, at $\Delta x \approx 16 \mu\text{m}$ there is a smaller energy spread and emittance, while the bunch energy as well as the charge are still relatively high and the maximum energy reaches its maximum for this Δx . So the optimal range found for this study is about $\Delta x = 0.7\lambda_p$. In [27], for $a_0 = 2$, $w_0 = 20 \lambda_L$, $\tau = 10.5 \lambda_L$, $\rho_{max}/\rho = 1.6$ and $\lambda_p = 15.8 \lambda_L$ an optimal down-ramp length of $\Delta x = 10 \lambda_L = 0.6\lambda_p$ is observed. This shows that a similar optimal setting for Δx could be found in the first scan as in [27].

Furthermore, it is observed that within the region of the gas the emittance for the filtered data is significantly higher than for those without a filter (see figure 5.2.2 segment 4 and figure 5.2.3, that remembers the energy filter in the energy-histogram). This can be explained by the fact that the emittance is calculated by averaging over the particles. In the case without the filter, all particles are included in the calculation. This also includes the slowly moving surrounding particles that form the wakefield. Since these slow particles make up a large part of all particles

Figure 5.2.3.: Energy histogram where the orange part shows which particles would disappear through the energy filter.

in the simulation, they reduce the momentum mean value as well as the average of the position and momentum in equation 3.6.9 and therefore the emittance. The same can be observed in the case without the filter when the electron beam leaves the gas and thus the slow surrounding particles. Therefore, figure 5.2.2 shows a steep increase of the emittance in segment 5. However, the emittance is still much larger than expected as it has a usual order of less than $1 \pi \text{ mm mrad}$ [72]. One reason for these high values is the choice of the Yee field-solver [56] of the maxwell equation within the PIConGPU algorithm. There an additional cherenkov radiation of the electrons is introduced as a numerical artifact, which leads to an expansion of the beam in the phase space and thus to a larger emittance. This can be avoided by choosing the Lehé field-solver [73], but it is less suitable for the calculation of charges and energies, because in this case the speed of the laser can be overestimated. For a more accurate result, further scans with different solvers of the PIC algorithm would have to be performed.

Since the focus position has no strong influence in this scan, the dependencies of the considered quantities can also be easily identified in one-dimensional plots that depend only on down-ramp length. These images are attached in A.0.1. In order to detect the influence of the focus position beyond the Rayleigh length, another scan was performed.

Second scan: long focus range

Even for range of focus positions used in this scan, the electron injection starts at the beginning of the density down-ramp and continues over the length of the

Figure 5.2.4.: Energy waterfall histogram shows the energy spectrum for focus position $940 \mu\text{m}$ behind the downramp and $\Delta x = 16$. The segments within the density profile (see figure 3.7.1) are marked with (1) - (3): up-ramp - down-ramp, (4): lower density plateau and (5): down-ramp leading into the vacuum.

down-ramp, regardless of the focus position.

As already described in the first scan for focus positions up to $0.3 z_R$ behind the down-ramp the **charge** is maximum for $\Delta x \approx 16 \mu\text{m}$ (see figure 5.2.5 (d)). For longer distances of the focus position from the down-ramp, the laser is too unfocused during the injection and a smaller charge is injected. The increase of the charge at a focus position of z_R behind the down-ramp is due to a second injection that is driven by the bunch of the first injection. This self-injection is triggered $0.3 z_R$ before the focus point. It becomes visible in the energy waterfall histograms in figure 5.2.4. Because self-injection is a difficult to control regime, and this thesis should study the down-ramp triggered injection, the focus position of one Rayleigh length behind the down-ramp is unfavourable.

Further results of this scan are shown in figure 5.2.5. It turns out that the maximum of the **bunch energy** at the smallest Δx occurs only for a laser focus $< 0.3 z_R$. Thus, for a later focus ($y > 350 \mu\text{m} \hat{=} 0.3 z_R$ behind the down-ramp) the profile of the laser at the point of the injection deviates too much from its shape in the focus to support the injection sufficiently. For a focus position that is about one Rayleigh length behind the down-ramp, figure 5.2.5 (a) shows an additional maximum for the bunch energy, but also for the energy spread and the emittance. This is due to the second injection.

Moreover figure 5.2.5 shows that the **maximum energy** and **energy spread** decreases with an increasing focus position.

Figure 5.2.5.: The second scan shows that in the range of $0.3z_R$ behind the down-ramp the charge and energy are highest. The second maximum at a focus position of about $900 \mu\text{m}$ is due to another self-injection. Results of second scan at $a_0 = 4.5$, $\lambda_L = 800 \text{ nm}$, $w_0^{FWHM} = 16 \mu\text{m}$, $\tau^{FWHM} = 28 \text{ fs}$, $\rho_{max}/\rho = 1,8$ and $\rho_{max} = 3.98 \cdot 10^{24} \text{ m}^{-3}$. Shows dependence on the length of the down-ramp Δx and focus position of (a) the bunch energy, (b) the energy spread, (c) the maximum energy, (d) the charge of the bunch and (e) the projected emittance.

For the **emittance**, there is a minimum in the region where the focus is farthest behind the down-ramp, where the bunch energy and maximum energy are also significantly lower. However, the emittance is also smaller for focus positions up to $0.3 z_R$ behind the down-ramp, where the bunch energy, maximum energy and the charge are higher.

So the focus position should be within the first 30 % of the Rayleigh length behind the down-ramp. Within this region, the position of the focus has almost no influence. Since only the region of the focus position is relevant, as already examined in the first scan, there are no new conclusions regarding the length of the down-ramp.

Third scan: laser strength parameter a_0

In figure 5.2.6 (a), it can be seen that the **bunch energy** becomes larger with increasing a_0 . This is due to the fact that the peak laser electric field amplitude E_L depends on a_0 as follows

$$E_L = m_e c \omega a_0 / e. \quad (5.2.1)$$

Thus the acceleration field is proportional to a_0 and in turn, the energies reached increases with a_0 .

In **comparison with the results of the first scan**, it is noticeable that here at $a_0 = 4.7$ the dependence of the bunch energy on the down-ramp length is less visible. In fact, the values are approximately the same as in the first scan, but the contrast is worse due to the larger value range of the bunch energy in the second scan. The same holds true for the emittance and charge. For $a_0 = 4.7$ a change of the emittance and charge regarding the down-ramp length is less visible than in the first scan. Figure 5.2.6 (d), (e) shows that the emittance and charge increase with a_0 . Thus, the increase of a_0 has more impact on the emittance, charge and the bunch energy than the length of the down-ramp. This can also be seen in figure A.0.3 (a), (d), (e), where the increase in bunch energy and emittance with a_0 is stronger than the spread of the points for different Δx for the same a_0 .

Furthermore, a **self-injection** occurs already in the density up-ramp (the first $20 \mu\text{m}$ of the density profile in figure 3.7.1) or the high density plateau (see (2) in figure 3.7.1) in most simulations. This leads to a small trapped charge, which undergoes a stronger acceleration gradient in the upper density plateau since the acceleration gradient is proportional to $\sqrt{\rho}$. This results in a small amount of electrons, which cause a higher energetic contribution in the energy waterfall

Figure 5.2.6.: The third scan shows that with increasing a_0 also the energies and the charge increase. With increasing charge the beam loading effect also becomes stronger. The results of the third scan at focus position $120 \mu\text{m}$ behind the down-ramp, $\lambda_L = 800 \text{ nm}$, $w_0^{FWHM} = 16 \mu\text{m}$, $\tau^{FWHM} = 28 \text{ fs}$, $\rho_{max}/\rho = 1,8$ and $\rho_{max} = 3.98 \cdot 10^{24} \text{ m}^{-3}$. Shows dependence on the length of the down-ramp Δx and the laser strength parameter a_0 (a) the bunch energy, (b) the energy spread, (c) the maximum energy, (d) the charge of the bunch and (e) the projected emittance.

histogram than in the bunches. Figure 5.2.7 shows that this contribution increases with larger a_0 . The up-ramp injection is described in [74] and can be avoided by a less steep increase towards the first plateau. This could not be implemented for the scan, as this would have additionally extended the simulation time. Thus the contribution of the up-ramp injection can be neglected. However, the electrons injected in the up-ramp reach the highest energies in the spectrum for $a_0 > 6.4$. Hence the maximum energy is also influenced by the up-ramp injection. Figure 5.2.7 shows that the maximum energy for $a_0 > 6.4$ increases. For smaller a_0 it is dominated by another small self-injection, that occurs at about 500 μm . At this point, a self-focusing of the laser occurs, which can be seen qualitatively in figure 5.2.8. Due to the self-focusing of the laser, the intensity at this point increases high enough so that the conditions for self-injection are fulfilled. The injected charge is driven by the first bunch and thus a higher acceleration gradient is applied to it and allows to reach higher energies than the down-ramp triggered bunch. This effect becomes weaker with increasing a_0 because with increasing a_0 also the **beam loading effect** (see section 3.3) increases.

As shown in figure 5.2.9, the bubble becomes more and more deformed by a higher charge, which also increases with a_0 , and cannot close. This prevents self-injection, as the bubble closes at a later point in time when the conditions for self-injection are no longer optimal. The beam loading effect also reduces the acceleration field for the down-ramp triggered bunch. This ensures an energetic spreading of the bunches and thus increases the energy spread. Since electrons are injected with long down-ramps over a longer period of time, a larger energy spread and charge is created at larger a_0 . This explains the increase in the energy spread seen in figure 5.2.6 with a_0 and for $a_0 \geq 6.4$ for larger Δx .

Figure 5.2.7.: These energy waterfall histograms are used to calculate the energy, charge and energy spread of the bunches as well as the maximum energy for eight values in the respective plots in figure 5.2.6. With a constant $\Delta x = 3 \mu\text{m}$ it can be seen that with increasing α_0 the influence of the self-injection in the deeper density plateau loses influence against the increasing energy of the electrons triggered in the initial self-injection and disappears for $\alpha_0 > 6.4$.

(a) Iteration 6400 at 266.7 μm (b) Iteration 13000 at 541.7 μm (c) Iteration 19100 at 795.9 μm

Figure 5.2.8.: In this illustration of the simulation box with the electron density (black) and laser electric field (green) it can be seen that self focusing occurs at around 550 μm

(a) $a_0 = 4.7$

(b) $a_0 = 6.4$

(c) $a_0 = 8.7$

(d) $a_0 = 10.4$

Figure 5.2.9.: This illustration of the simulation box with the electron density (black) and laser electric field (green) at iteration 10000 shows that the beam loading effect increases for larger a_0 as indicated by the deformation and elongation of the bubble.

6. Conclusion and Outlook

The research area of laser wakefield acceleration is characterized by non-linear processes, which complicate the search for optimal input parameters for a stable and best possible beam quality. With simulations, it is possible to search for optimal points in the parameter space, but this is not possible in an acceptable time and with an acceptable amount of memory if all particle and field data are stored. With in-situ analyses, it is possible to perform a large part of the analysis during the simulation time, which saves a lot of time. At the same time, the amount of data can be reduced as not all particle and field data have to be stored. Thus, the simulation time and the memory requirements reach a level where systematic studies are possible.

In this master thesis, both an in-situ analysis for the determination of emittance as well as the slice emittance and a tool for the simple execution of systematic studies were developed. Afterwards, a parameter scan was performed and analyzed to prove the functionality of the new tool.

The PIconGPU GUI is opened via an online browser and allows to easily set simulation parameters and start a variety of simulations simultaneously. The parameters are set automatically and the PIconGPU simulations placed in the compile and run queue. Also, the status of the simulation could be checked with the GUI. In the evaluation, the GUI helped to compare different visualizations of different simulations with each other.

In this thesis, it was used for to perform large parameter scans. In the regime of the density down-ramp injection the influence of the focus position of the laser, the laser strength parameter a_0 and the length of the density down-ramp Δx on the energy, energy spread and charge of the injected electron bunch as well as the maximum energy reached and the projected emittance were determined.

It turns out, that the bunch energy becomes maximal for smaller down-ramp lengths Δx . Due to the fact that the peak laser electric field amplitude E_L is proportional to a_0 and thus a higher acceleration gradient is available and the bunch energy increases with a_0 . Furthermore, the bunch energy is maximal for a focus position between the beginning of the down-ramp and about $1/5 z_R$ behind it. This can be explained by the fact that the laser profile changes only slightly in this region.

Analogous, the highest maximal energy ($E_{max} = 460$ MeV) and the bunch charge ($Q = 0.83$ nC) for $a_0 = 4.5$ can be found for the same region of the focus position and a down-ramp length of $\Delta x \approx 0.7 \lambda_p$. Due to the linear dependency of the peak laser electric field amplitude E_L on a_0 (see equation 5.2.1), these values increase further with a_0 up to $E_{max} > 500$ MeV and $Q > 2.5$ nC for $a_0 = 11$. However, it also shows that the increase in energy does not increase linearly with a_0 .

The emittance is slightly lower for $22 \mu\text{m} < \Delta x < 53 \mu\text{m}$ and increases with a_0 , where the change of a_0 has the greater influence. Only for a focus position far behind the down-ramp ($\approx 1400 \mu\text{m}$) the emittance is reduced. The energy spread is reduced by approximately 55 MeV at $22 \mu\text{m} < \Delta x < 34 \mu\text{m}$ and $a_0 = 4.5$. For a focus up to $1/5 z_R$ behind the down-ramp, the energy spread is increased. The lower energy spread and emittance for middle down-ramp lengths can be explained by the fact that for larger Δx wave breaking takes place in a slower manner and the breaking takes place over a longer period of time. Without the injection taking too long to get a wide energy range.

Furthermore, it could be determined that for $a_0 > 5$ beam loading effects occur, which prevent an additional self-injection shortly after the down-ramp. But such a self-injection is possible if the focus position is about one Rayleigh length behind the down-ramp.

The three scans also show the complex nonlinear behavior of the parameters. So it is not easy to find a comprehensive optimal point where both the energies as well as the charge are maximum and at the same time the energy spread and emittance are low. Also it is not always known before starting a scan which resolution and which range has to be chosen. When choosing a larger range with a lower resolution, a local extremum can easily be overlooked. But if a smaller area with a higher resolution is chosen, it is not sure if there would have been an extremum outside the area.

Moreover, it should be noted that the second density plateau and thus the acceleration range can be extended even further without reaching the depletion or dephasing length (see section 3.1, 3.3) and therefore a higher bunch energy,

maximal energy and charge can be expected with a longer runtime. In this work, the maximum acceleration length was not applied in order to be able to perform many simulations for larger parameter scans with shorter simulation times. It was possible to run four simulations with 6h simulation time simultaneously, which means a total simulation time of approximately 450 h (less than three weeks) for 300 simulations. In these scans, 16 GPUs were used for one simulation. If more resources are used, the duration of a simulation can be shortened significantly and it is thus possible to perform more extensive parameter scans, which not only cover a larger range but also have a better resolution due to more sample points. Furthermore, it is conceivable to automatically search for optimal parameter sets with the help of optimization methods, e.g. machine learning. Here not all parameter ranges would have to be divided evenly into sample points, but at interesting places, more points can be, than in less interesting regions. In addition, systematic studies can be used for sensitivity analyses to investigate how uncertainties of input parameters affect the outcome of a numerical simulation.

In the future, the GUI will be connected to RODARE (rossendorf data repository), which allows an open access to the HZDR research data. Thus it will be possible to publish the scan data on the publication platform RODARE. To make the research data uniquely citeable it is assigned to a Digital Object Identifier (DOI). Via a OAI-PMH interface, the data can be uploaded. By also publishing all associated research and metadata via RODARE it enables other researchers to reproduce the already published results. With this connection of the PIConGPU GUI and RODARE, it will be possible to generate the data sustainable and reusable. More precisely, it is even possible to comply with the FAIR principle. This is a guiding principle to make data **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable [75]. In order to derive the greatest benefit from the research data, it addresses data producers and data publishers. To be findable the data includes rich metadata, a unique and persistent identifier and are searchable. If the scan data is stored in RODARE together with its metadata, it becomes citable and searchable, thus fulfilling the principle of findable data. Moreover, the metadata is accessible through the OAI-PMH interface as well as the public REST API, even if data files are no longer available. The principle of interoperability is satisfied because the metadata is represented using the JSON schema and referenced with resolvable URL. To be reusable the data in RODARE contains the terms of the DataCite Metadata Scheme and a license term for Open Access and Embargoed records. For further details see [76].

Furthermore, the simulation data will be assignable to different scans, as new

groups will include a user-defined collection of simulations. This results in a direct reuse of the simulation data. Good data management by coupling the PIconGPU GUI to RODARE gives the opportunity for data and knowledge integration and reuse. Thus outcomes of different research groups can be combined and the outcomes can be made available to the community. This also results in a further planned extension of the GUI, which provides an interface to combine simulations to new groups. These functionalities will be integrated in another third tab, next to "submission" and "visualisation".

Further extensions of the GUI are possible through the integration of further visualizers. This can be done with plugins, such as the new emittance plugin. In the context of this master thesis, a new emittance plugin could be developed, and three additional visualizers (evolution of projected emittance, slice emittance and waterfall histogram of slice emittance) are integrated into the GUI. Moreover a new plugin to generate a coherent transition radiation (CTR) - spectrum is planned. Furthermore, the GUI can also be used and adapted for applications other than LWFA. Thus, other simulation scenarios such as "Emission of Bremsstrahlung from Laser-Foil Interaction", "Thomson scattering from laser electron-bunch interaction", "Ion Acceleration from a Liquid-Crystal Target" and "Kelvin-Helmholtz Instability" will be possible with the same back-end.

A. Further scan representations

Figure A.0.1.: Results of scan 1 at $a_0 = 4.5$, $\lambda = 800 \text{ nm}$, $w_0^{FWHM} = 16 \mu\text{m}$, $\tau^{FWHM} = 28 \text{ fs}$, $\rho_{max}/\rho = 1,8$ and $\rho_{max} = 3.98 \cdot 10^{24} \text{ m}^{-3}$. Shows depending on the length of the down-ramp Δx and for different focus positions (a) the bunch energy, (b) the energy spread, (c) the maximum energy, (d) the charge of the bunch and (e) the projected emittance.

Figure A.0.2.: Results of scan 2 at $a_0 = 4.5$, $\lambda = 800 \text{ nm}$, $w_0^{FWHM} = 16 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, $\tau^{FWHM} = 28 \text{ fs}$, $\rho_{max}/\rho = 1, 8$ and $\rho_{max} = 3.98 \cdot 10^{24} \text{ m}^{-3}$. Shows depending on the length of the down-ramp Δx and for different focus positions (a) the bunch energy, (b) the energy spread, (c) the maximum energy, (d) the charge of the bunch and (e) the projected emittance.

Figure A.0.3.: Results of scan 3 at focus position 120 μm behind the down-ramp, $\lambda = 800$ nm, $w_0^{FWHM} = 16$ μm, $\tau^{FWHM} = 28$ fs, $\rho_{max}/\rho = 1,8$ and $\rho_{max} = 3.98 \cdot 10^{24} m^{-3}$. Shows depending on the laser strength parameter a_0 and for different down-ramp length Δx and (a) the bunch energy, (b) the energy spread, (c) the maximum energy, (d) the charge of the bunch and (e) the projected emittance.

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